

Performance of IR64 in Karnataka, India

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We tested IR64 (selected from the cross IR5657-33-2-1/IR2061-465-1-5-5, designated IR18348-36-3-3) in trials of the All India Network of the Directorate of Rice Research, under IET no. 9671. It yielded 4.0-8.7 t/ha in different states and is already popular with farmers in Andhra Pradesh and parts of Orissa and Karnataka.

In Karnataka, yield trials were conducted in both the wet (WS) and dry seasons (DS).

Under Bangalore and Mysore conditions in the rainy season, duration was

125-135 d, but a week earlier under Shimoga and Chitradurga conditions. Duration was 4-5 d longer in DS. In experimental farm trials 1988-90, mean grain yields ranged from 6.8 t/ha in DS to 6.2 t/ha in WS. Even when transplanted the third week of Aug in WS, it produced 4 t/ha, compared to 3.0-3.5 t/ha of other short-duration varieties. It failed to perform well when it was planted as late as Sep and Oct. No serious pest or disease incidence was observed when it was planted in Jun-Jul in WS and Jan-Feb in DS. In late WS at Bangalore, blast disease attacked many varieties, but was not found on IR64. It scored 2 against 7 for susceptible check S317 for leaf blast. It had no neck blast.

In irrigated farmers' fields in Mysore, Hassan, Chitradurga, and

Shimoga districts, grain yields ranged from 6.2 to 7.5 t/ha against 6.0-6.5 t/ha for emergency Sona, Rasi, Madhu, Telhamsa, and Jyothi.

Height is 70 to 90 cm, depending on the season. Tillering ability is moderate, but grains/panicle, grain-filling percentage, and grain weight are on the high side, implying that they are the characteristics contributing to yield.

Grain is slender with straw-colored husk, and has been found to be very good for puffing, which earns a premium in the market. Grains do not have any pigmentation or abdominal white, making the variety attractive to consumers. Brown rice recovery is 77-78% and head rice recovery 60-67%. Cooking quality was judged good by a taste panel that included farmers. ■

Ptb 46 (KAU1727), a high-yielding, widely adaptable rice variety from Kerala, India

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KAU1727, a short-duration, semidwarf rice culture from the cross Triveni/IR2061, was identified as high-yielding with multiple resistances and wide adaptability. It has been released as Ptb 46 in Kerala.

The 120-d variety has white slender grains and is suitable for all three seasons in Kerala.

In 1983, KAU1727 was evaluated in the International Rice Yield Nursery (IRYN) early group at 37 sites in 18 countries (see table). It ranked first among 25 elite breeding lines with an average yield of 5.3 t/ha. In 1984, the culture ranked second with a mean yield of 5.1 t/ha. Average yield of check variety IR36 was 4.8 and 4 t/ha, respectively.

In screening trials at IRRI, KAU1727 exhibited resistance to all three brown planthopper biotypes. In multilocation

Performance of KAU1727 in 1983 and 1984 International Rice Yield Nursery.

Location	1983		1984	
	Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (t/ha)	Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (t/ha)
Southeast Asia	87	4.8	87	4.1
South Asia	97	5.0	101	5.2
East Asia	110	7.2		
West Asia and North Africa	104	8.4	112	10.3
Latin America			86	4.9
Overall	94	5.3	94	5.1

trials, it exhibited resistance to green leafhopper, blast, bacterial leaf streak, and leafhopper. In trials at Pattambi, ratooning ability was highly promising. ■

Contribution of IR36 to new varieties in Hunan, China

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Xiang-Zhong Xian No. 2, a derivative of the cross Ai-Bao/IR36/Shuang-Gui 36, released in Dec 1989, is a high-yielding indica rice variety. It performed well in 1987-89 regional trials in monocropped midseason rice areas.

Average grain yield was 8.3 t/ha, 2.4% higher than that of high-yielding

hybrid rice Shan-You 63. Average growth duration was 133 d in Hunan, 5 d earlier than Shan-You 63. It is resistant to whitebacked planthopper and brown planthopper and moderately resistant to rice blast and sheath blight. Xiang-Zhong Xian No. 2 also has resistance to lodging and good response to high levels of fertilizer.

In 1990, Xiang-Zhong Xian No. 2 was grown in 16,667 ha in Hunan. In midseason cropping, it yielded an average 7.5-7.9 t/ha, with the record 10.5 t/ha. In late rice cropping, it yielded 6.6-8.2 t/ha, with the highest 9.8 t/ha.

One reason Xiang-Zhong Xian No. 2 has such high yield potential and multiple resistance is the contribution of IR36's excellent resistance and agronomic characters. ■

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.